

**ISSUES OF ENSURING THE ADMISSIBILITY OF RESULTS
OBTAINED THROUGH THE USE OF DIGITAL PHOTO AND
VIDEO RECORDING MEANS DURING INVESTIGATIVE
ACTIONS**

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Abstract: The article focuses on the issues related to the use of photo and video technical means for digital documentation of visual information in investigative activities and its criminal procedural formalization to obtain admissible evidence.

Keywords: technical means, photo and video equipment, admissible evidence, investigative activities.

*Ensuring full digitalization of activities related
to the collection and preservation of evidence
through the implementation of modern technologies
and the latest scientific advancements.*

(STRATEGY "Uzbekistan - 2030") [1]

In the past decade, digital technology has been actively utilized in investigative, expert, and operational-search activities. In investigative practice, it serves as an additional tool for recording the progress and results of investigative actions. The use of digital technology demonstrates the effectiveness of the obtained results and the convenience of its application. Therefore, law enforcement agencies consider this activity one of the priority areas in preventing, detecting, and investigating crimes.

It should be noted that for the results obtained through digital photo and video cameras to be considered sources of evidence in a case, they must be obtained in accordance with the procedure established by criminal procedure law and be admissible. Previously, there were almost no issues regarding the admissibility of photographs and video recordings obtained using analog technical means as evidence. However, with the widespread implementation of digital technology in law enforcement activities, such issues are becoming increasingly common [2]. New technologies have quickly gained recognition among practitioners in criminal procedural activities. However, they have also raised new concerns regarding methods of preserving the reliability of information obtained during investigative actions. This is because, unlike analog equipment previously used, digital cameras do not record information on film but rather on electronic storage devices. The data recorded on these devices is easier to edit when an external storage device is connected to a computer. Therefore, to ensure the integrity of the originally obtained information (preventing its modification or destruction), a reliable mechanism must be in place to preserve its original content.

This issue is particularly significant in light of discussions on replacing the institution of attesting witnesses in certain investigative actions with procedural recording of these actions using technical means. These technical means are specifically digital since they significantly outperform analog devices.

According to Part 4, Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the use of evidence obtained in violation of the law, i.e., criminal procedure legislation, is not permitted. This constitutional provision is reinforced in Articles 95 and 951 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CPC RU) and is expressed, first, in the mandatory evaluation of each piece of evidence in terms of its admissibility (Part 3, Article 95 CPC), ensuring that they are collected in compliance with the conditions set forth in Articles 88, 90, 92–94 of the CPC RU. Second, it requires recognizing evidence as inadmissible (Article 951 CPC) if it has been obtained unlawfully [3]. This means that the loss of evidence deemed inadmissible can negatively impact the outcome of a criminal case. Therefore, it is essential to strictly adhere to all the necessary provisions of the CPC RU when collecting evidence. This particularly applies to the use of digital

technology in conducting investigative actions. The issue is increasingly relevant due to the rapid advancement of science and technology, as well as the gradual replacement of analog photo and video recording methods with digital equipment.

The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CPC RU) does not provide a precise definition of the concept of admissibility of evidence. Part 3 of Article 95 of the CPC RU merely refers to evidence obtained in violation of the requirements of the CPC RU (Articles 88, 90, 92–94), which is deemed inadmissible. Based on this, the admissibility of obtained evidence is assessed as a strictly formal concept, meaning compliance of the source of factual data and its procedural form with the requirements established by law. Evidence is collected from the sources listed in Part 2 of Article 81 in accordance with Article 87 of the CPC RU.

In general, four main criteria determine the compliance of evidence with the procedural form in criminal proceedings, i.e., its admissibility:

- 1) The evidence must be obtained by a duly authorized subject of proof.
- 2) The evidence must be obtained from a source provided for by criminal law.
- 3) The procedure established by criminal law must be observed.

4) The process of obtaining evidence must be documented in accordance with the requirements of Article 90 of the CPC RU.

These criteria are taken into account when assessing the admissibility of any piece of evidence. If evidence is obtained in violation of any of these criteria, it is recognized as inadmissible.

In most cases, photographs obtained using analog equipment do not raise doubts about their admissibility in criminal proceedings, provided that all requirements of the CPC RU are met. However, the same cannot be said about the results of digital means used to record investigative actions. It is well known that modern digital photo and video cameras can process images, including uncontrolled modifications by users, leading to doubts about their reliability. These doubts arise due to non-compliance with the legally established procedure and conditions for the use of technical means in investigative and procedural actions, as well as improper packaging of digital storage media [4]. As a result, questions emerge regarding the admissibility of such evidence in criminal proceedings.

Digital images obtained during an investigative action become vulnerable to modifications when the photo or video device is connected to a computer, as computer software allows for the distortion of the original information. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the sequence of

actions for an expert (investigator) after obtaining digital images on the relevant equipment to ensure their immutability and, consequently, their reliability.

The mechanism, timeframe, location, and methods of processing information obtained through photography are not specified in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CPC RU). The absence of such regulation has led to the opinion that it is necessary to establish, at the normative level, the conditions and procedures for using technical means during investigative actions, the objects to which these means are applied, and the results obtained [5]. Since the legislator currently leaves this matter to science and practice, the procedures followed by an expert (investigator) are based on scientific recommendations and practical experience. For instance, the CPC RU specifies the requirement to attach negatives, photographs, and computer data carriers to the protocol of an investigative action. In practice, negatives are produced after the protocol is prepared, as are photo tables, and this procedure does not raise objections from the court regarding the preliminary investigation bodies. In the case of digital photography, it is preferable to prepare the photo table before the completion of the investigative action, have it signed by all participants with the date and time of creation indicated, and attach an electronic image carrier to the protocol, packed in a manner that prevents unauthorized access to the image.

It should be noted that this presents certain technical difficulties: first, the need for a portable computer with a printer, and second, significant costs for memory cards. Despite the wide variety of memory cards that have recently appeared, it remains simpler and more cost-effective to use CD-R (DVD-R) discs. These are relatively inexpensive, unaffected by magnetic fields, and thus prevent the loss of recorded information. The cost of such a disc is lower than that of photographic film in analog photography.

Before beginning an investigative action, the CD-R disc to be used must be labeled with an individual number. After the shooting, the recorded images must be reviewed, with the number of frames and their content documented in the protocol of the investigative action. In the presence of witnesses, the disc is then sealed, labeled with an explanatory note, stamped, and certified with the signatures of the investigator and the witnesses. Additionally, the protocol must document any transfer of information onto another type of storage medium.

To include the obtained photographs in the case materials, the disc must be examined, and photographs produced from it, without requiring the presence of witnesses. The opinion that non-rewritable discs should be used as data carriers is supported by a number of other scholars.

Digital technical means used during investigative actions must be recorded in the protocol in accordance with Parts 2–4 of Article 91 of the CPC RU. Summarizing the requirements

regarding which specific details about technical means must be included in the protocol, it can be concluded that the protocol should specify the name of the technical device, its type, screen resolution, brand, model, manufacturer, type of flash card, CD-R (DVD-R) disc, or other electronic storage medium, its capacity, and whether or not it contains any images. Additionally, all operations performed with the technical device, the physical electronic storage medium, and the obtained results must be documented. All other necessary information for inclusion in the protocol is outlined in Parts 2–4 of Article 91 of the CPC RU and does not differ from the details recorded in the protocol for analog photography.

The identified issues related to preserving the integrity of information obtained through digital recording may be resolvable. By implementing the proposed recommendations, positive results can be achieved and successfully used in the process of proof. It is likely that, over time, technology will continue to advance, and today's challenges will be resolved in simpler ways.

References:

1. See Clause 87 of Appendix No. 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023, No. UP-158, "Strategy Uzbekistan-2030" // <https://www.prezident.uz>.

2. On the implementation of advanced scientific and technical means and information and communication technologies in the law enforcement agencies of Uzbekistan, see: Presidential Decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Decree dated October 21, 2016, No. UP-4850, "On Measures for the Further Reform of the Judicial and Legal System, Strengthening Guarantees for the Reliable Protection of Citizens Rights and Freedoms" (Clause 1) // <https://www.prezident.uz>; Decree dated March 26, 2019, No. UP-6196, "On Measures to Elevate the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies to a Qualitatively New Level in Ensuring Public Security and Combating Crime" (Clause 8) // <https://www.prezident.uz>; and others.

3. See also: Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 24, 2018, No. 24, "On Certain Issues of Applying Criminal Procedure Law Provisions Regarding the Admissibility of Evidence" // <https://www.sud.uz>.

4. See, for example: NasyMov E.D., Shulgin E.P., Abeuov D.A., "The Impact of Digitalization on Law Enforcement Activities in the Republic of Kazakhstan" // Khabarshi - Vestnik. – 2023. - No. 2 (80). – Pp. 176-177.

5. It should be noted that Articles 911-914 of the CPC RU define the regulations governing the recording of the course and results of investigative actions conducted via videoconference.